

Contextualising 1 Corinthians 4:1-2 as a Psychological Model for Stewardship in the Nigerian Polity

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Abstract

The paper examines 1 Corinthians 4:1-2 as a psychological model for stewardship in Nigerian political system. The study was informed by the fact that though democracy is commonly considered to be the government that is ushered by the people for the betterment of the people; this assertion as good as it is seems to be far from reality in Nigerian political system. The study, using secondary source of materials, employed the use of biblical historical criticism while applying exegetical rule of context in contextualising 1 Corinthians 4:1-2 as a psychological model for stewardship in Nigerian political system. The study adopted Reciprocal Determinism as a theoretical framework which was propounded by Albert Bandura. The theory states that a person's behaviour both influences and is influenced by personal factors and the social environment. Thus, the study finds out a psychological gap between the ideals of democracy and what the politicians practice as democracy in Nigerian political system. The study recommends among other recommendations the need for behavioural change from the electorate first and the politician using 1 Corinthians 4:1-2 as model. Also, the study recommends the need for religious leaders to take the front Bonner for the said behavioural change of their subjects who doubles as both the masses and the political class.

Keywords: Context, Psychology, Model, Stewardship and Politics

Introduction

One of the most daunting problems which have stunted the growth of Nigeria democratically and advance its stability is the lack of adherence to ethos, rule of law and constitutionality.¹ For over 60 years since it gained independence, Nigeria has found it difficult to attain democratic stability despite efforts by past administrations to achieve this feat. The inability of Nigeria's past and present leadership to consolidate on the gains of democracy has been attributed to lack of stewardship in governance and corruption. In general terms, corruption has eaten very deep and hence, found its way into the body polity of the Nigerian state so much so that virtually all spheres of the nation's life stinks with the sores of corruption. The effects of corruption on the socioeconomic, cultural and political landscape of Nigeria government can be so devastating that nothing meaningful works in the midst of this malaise. Corruption therefore becomes a clog in the wheel of progress of any nation state if the menace is not controlled.

Over the years, the Nigerian Mass Media have uncovered and revealed to the nation cases of corruption on a massive scale, a situation that is not only highly abhorred but reprehensible to well-meaning Nigerians. However, the ugly practice persisted and has steadily made very deep in-roads in every spheres of our national life.² Virtually all private, public and political spheres have been permeated and contaminated by corruption. This kind of development as pointed above compelled Preye and Weleayam to argue that Nigerians no longer believe that honesty and integrity are worthy principles since one can do very little or even do nothing at all to gain so much.³ The school of thought of Preye and Weleayam on the high degree of ineptitude and indolence in the

attitude of Nigerians further confirms the fact that corruption is not a thing of the leadership alone. The followership is also guilty as it is culpable for this misdemeanor.

Thus, one finds corruption showing its face in the affairs of the family circle, schools (primary, secondary and universities and other higher structures of learning); worship places, the bureaucracy, security outfits, market places, main stream politics, village meetings, women organisations, electoral activities, appointment of persons into public offices; the manner and character in which funds are disbursed from the centre to states and local councils, rigging of elections, and many more. All of these stages and categories of corruption have over the years constituted themselves into a huge albatross bedeviling the Nigerian state. Corruption whether political, economic, judicial, familial, institutional or bureaucratic could by and large impede the progress of any society where such attitudes are widely tolerated and accommodated in the scheme of things. Should unfaithfulness and corruption continue in Nigeria? This question is indeed a propelling factor for the choice of this topic especially now that the cases of corruption, misappropriation of funds and lack of accountability for public funds and resources are becoming more alarming by the day in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This paper adopts Reciprocal Determinism, propounded by Albert Bandura in 1973 and further developed in 1977 as the theoretical framework upon which this discourse hinges. Albert Bandura graduated from the University of British Columbia with a degree in Psychology in the year 1949. He received his Ph.D. in Clinical Psychology from the University of Iowa in 1952. After he finished his PhD because of his famous studies and searches Bandura was elected as the president of the American Psychological Association in 1974. He was also elected as the outstanding lifetime contribution to Psychology, American Psychological Association in 2004. Bandura has earned the title of “Father of the Cognitive Theory.”⁴

One of the most important aspects of Bandura’s view on how personality is learned is that each one of us is an agent of change, fully participating in our surroundings and influencing the environmental contingencies that behaviourists believe affect our behaviour. These interactions can be viewed in three different ways. The first is to consider behaviour as a function of the person and the environment. In this view, personal dispositions (or traits) and the consequences of our actions (reinforcement or punishment) combine to cause our behaviour. This perspective is closest to the radical behaviourism of Skinner. The second view considers that personal dispositions and the environment interact, and the result of the interaction causes our behaviour, a view somewhat closer to that of Dollard and Miller. In each of these perspectives, behaviour is caused, or determined, by dispositional and environmental factors, the behaviour itself is not a factor in how that behaviour comes about. However, according to Bandura, social learning theory emphasises that behaviour, personal factors, and environmental factors are all equal, interlocking determinants of each other. This concept is referred to as “reciprocal determinism.”⁵⁶

Reciprocal determinism can be seen in everyday observations, such as those made by Bandura and others during their studies of aggression. For example, approximately 75 percent of the time, hostile behaviour results in unfriendly responses, whereas friendly acts seldom result in such consequences. With little effort, it becomes easy to recognise individuals who create negative social climates.⁷ Thus, while it may still be true that changing environmental contingencies changes behaviour, it is also true that changing behaviour alters the environmental contingencies. This results in a unique perspective on freedom vs. determinism. Usually we think of determinism as something that eliminates or restricts our freedom. However, Bandura believed that individuals can intentionally act as agents of change within their environment, thus altering the factors that determine their behaviour. In other words, we have the freedom to influence that which determines our behaviour. Reciprocal determinism is relevant to this study because it gives insight on how our behaviour interacts with our environment and our personality variables to influence our life. It further explains the freedom we have as individuals to influence that which determines our behaviour.

Conceptual Clarifications

Sometimes the word steward is misunderstood to mean a term of reproach and insinuates that the person called a steward is an ignoramus, a degraded person, an errand boy and a mere flunky. This understanding could have been reached due to certain lexicographers who have said that the word steward originally meant keeper of the pigsty, but the Oxford Dictionary of English Language refutes the above understanding by saying that it means a manager or an administrator. Stewardship refers to the act of keeping or managing of the house, or act of overseeing of an estate, the act of one who employed servants, catered at banquets, a representative of the master of a business or the courts.⁸ Also a steward may be a person who serves on a large estate to manage domestic concerns such as collecting rent, handling accounts, directing servants.

Generally, in the New Testament, two Greek words embody the meaning of the English word stewardship. The first word is *epitropos* which means manager, foreman, or steward. From the standpoint of government, it means governor or procurator. At times it was used in the New Testament to mean guardian (Galatians 4:1-2). The second word is *oikonomos*. It also means steward, manager, or administrator and occurs more frequently in the New Testament. Depending on the context, it is often translated “dispensation, stewardship, management, arrangement, administration, order, plan, or training.” It refers mostly to the law or management of a household or of household affairs.⁹ Moreover, another concept that needs to be clarified is the term “Nigerian Polity.” According to Cambridge dictionary, the word polity refers to a society or state considered as a political unit. In other words, polity is a term for an identifiable political entity, defined as a group of people with a collective identity, who are organized by some form of institutionalised social relations, and have a capacity to mobilise resources. Therefore, the term Nigerian polity simply refers to Nigeria as a political entity.

The Need for Stewardship in the Nigerian Polity

The emphasis of faithful stewardship is long overdue in Nigeria. There are some traces of unfaithfulness in both sacred and secular leadership in Nigeria. No proper accountability to the people of Nigeria by political office holders.

Although, some governors do organize town hall meetings in their states to give some shallow accounts of their governance to the people, resources expended on reported projects seems not to commensurate with what is empirically seen on ground by the ordinary citizens. Sometimes, some projects are not awarded according to the rule of law. Many average Nigerians do not know how much is entering and going out the national and state coffers either monthly or annually. It is so because no law compels political leaders in Nigeria to give account to that effect.¹⁰ In Nigeria today, over 2.4 million barrels of crude oil is being produced per day.¹¹ Yet, large numbers of Nigerian population are living in abject poverty due to mismanagement of the nation’s resources over the years.

Corruption in both sacred and secular spheres of Nigeria has been identified as the destroyer of the nation’s socio-economic and political lives. Our integrities seemed to be arousing questions and begging for answers in international socio-political, socio-cultural and socio-economic climes. The stigma of corruption is affecting the people of Nigeria in such way that when a Nigerian is passing through any international boarder, such Nigerian is given a very humiliating search. Transparency International consistently rates the levels of corruption in Nigeria among the highest in the world. Pervasive corruption appears to permeate many levels of the Nigerian society. The rate of political corruption in Nigeria is progressively increasing with an upsurge in the number of cases where apparatus of government has become an instrument for the enrichment of members of political elites and that from pre-independence era to date, political corruption and its attendant problems in forms of vote buying, election rigging and manipulation, outright embezzlement by politicians have negatively affected the lives of Nigerians.¹² This has led to increased political apathy and distrust in the country’s fledging democratic ideals. Political corruption remains the major challenge of governance in Nigeria and that political corruption negatively impacts other strata of governance such as security, education, energy and power and other sectors.¹³

Some political leaders who gave the impression or promised to eradicate corruption are being seen to be speaking with the two sides of the mouth. The state and National Houses of Assemblies are saddled with the responsibility of making laws and making sure that such laws are being faithfully implemented but it is amazing to see that some of those politicians who make the laws are the same people who break the laws. It appears institutions such as the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC), the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC), etc. are not well empowered enough to handle corruption in Nigeria. This is why it appears as if they cannot prosecute certain people in Nigeria.¹⁴ Nigerian political leaders have planted and nurtured corruption. It has also spread to the civil service, church and the common people in the street. This is probably why Achebe sates that “Nigerians are corrupt because the system under which they live today makes corruption easy and profitable; they will cease to be corrupt when corruption is made difficult and inconvenient.”¹⁵ That Nigeria is very rich and the majority of her citizens are living in abject poverty is indeed a paradox that beats the imagination of the entire humanity. The suffering of many Nigerians in the midst of wealth is a product of gross mismanagement of the nation’s human and material resources by political leaders.

Hence, Achebe further asserts that the “Nigerian problem is the unwillingness or inability of its leaders to rise to their responsibility, to the challenge of personal example which is the hallmarks of true leadership.”¹⁶ The challenge of personal example is in the thought of Achebe of great importance but unfortunately it has not been so. Achebe’s theory of leadership failure is one of the most frequently quoted statements about Nigeria. It was a damning critique of Nigerian elites that has continued to resound even after three decades that the notion of an overarching leadership failure as the root of our society’s ills has almost become a cliché trotted out by everyone including successive generations of leaders to explain our chronic national underperformance. Ochuba agrees with Achebe that Nigeria has a problem with leadership and insists that there can be no serious change in the country unless it occurs in the leadership. For him, if people see their political leaders as little more than robbers of the state, what prevents them from developing the same instinct in their lives? The burden of translating dreams of true progress and independence to reality lies on the Nigerian leaders. This is development, he holds.¹⁷ Without a doubt, the need for us to evolve a new paradigm of leadership on our shores has never been more urgent.

A Background 1 Corinthians

Paul wrote this letter, as well as Second Corinthians, from Ephesus during his third missionary journey, perhaps in 56 AD.¹⁸ After his visit to Athens, where the apostle made his famous speech at the Areopagus during his second journey (49-52 AD.), he went on to Corinth in about 51 AD (Acts 18:1). Corinth was situated on the Isthmus of Greece (called Achaia in the Bible) between the Ionian Sea and the Aegean Sea, above the Mediterranean Sea. About 50 miles to the east was the city of Athens. The Corinth of Paul’s day was relatively new. The old Corinth (which was famous and powerful in the days of the Peloponnesian War) was burned in 146 B.C. by the Roman proconsul, L. Mummius. Because it was a city devoted to the gods, a hundred years were required to pass before the city could be rebuilt. In 46 B.C., Julius Caesar rebuilt the city, populated it with a colony of veterans and freedmen, and named it Julia Corinthus.¹⁹ It soon became a very important commercial center. With a population of 400,000 and being a prominent center of commerce in the Mediterranean world, it was a place for all sorts of vice. An example of its immorality was found in the temple of Venus (Aphrodite), which hosted 1000 priestesses dedicated to prostitution in the name of religion. The city’s close proximity to the city of Athens probably added the problem of intellectualism. As noticed in the epistle, such an environment had its effect upon the church in Corinth. It is amazing that a church existed at all in such a city.

The establishment of the church occurred during Paul’s second missionary journey. It is recorded by Luke in Ac 18:1-18, which can be divided into three sections:

- i. Abiding with Aquila and Priscilla, fellow tentmakers; reasoning in the synagogue every Sabbath (Acts 18:1-6).
- ii. In the house of Justus, abiding there and teaching for a year and six months (Acts 18:7-11).
- iii. An incident before Gallio, proconsul of Achaia (Ac 18:12-18).

It appears from reading the epistle that the church was adversely affected by the immoral environment found in the city. Pride caused division in the church and disruption in the services (1 Cor. 1-4, 11). Immorality and immodesty found its way into the church, which gave it a bad reputation (1 Cor. 5). The brethren were taking their personal problems with each other before the heathen courts instead of working them out among themselves (1 Cor. 6). Other issues affecting the church included questions about marriage (1 Cor. 7), meats sacrificed to idols (1 Cor. 8-10), women praying and prophesying with heads uncovered (1 Cor. 11), abusing the Lord's Supper (1 Cor. 11), the use of spiritual gifts (1 Cor. 12-14), the resurrection from the dead (1 Cor. 15), and the collection for the saints in Jerusalem (1 Cor. 16). Thus the church was one beset with problems and questions that needed to be answered.

Paul wrote this letter in response to a report from Chloe's people about problems in the Corinthian church (1:11). In this letter, he provides apostolic guidance for dealing with those problems. Among the problems that Paul has addressed are divisions in the Corinthian church based, in part, on allegiances to Paul or Apollos (3:4). He has also addressed the tendency of some of these Christians to trust in human wisdom rather than the cross of Christ (1:18 – 2:16).

Textual Analysis of 1 Corinthians 4:1-2

The Greek text of 1 Corinthians 4:1-2 reads:

1. οὕτως ἡμᾶς λογιζέσθω ἄνθρωπος ὡς ὑπηρετάς Χριστοῦ καὶ οἰκονόμους μυστηρίων θεοῦ. 2 ὧδε λοιπὸν ζητεῖται ἐν τοῖς οἰκονόμοις ἵνα πιστός τις εὐρεθῇ.

While the English translation reads:

1. This is how one should regard us, as servants of Christ and stewards of the mysteries of God. 2 Moreover, it is required of stewards that they be found faithful. (1 Cor. 4:1-2, ESV).

“This is how one should regard us” (v. 1a). In verse 6, Paul says, I have applied all this to Apollos and myself for your benefit,” so the “us” in this verse refers to Paul and Apollos.

“as servants (*hyperetes*) of Christ” (v. 1b). The words most often used in the New Testament for servant are *diakonos* (the word from which we get our word “deacon”) and *doulos* (a word closer to “slave” than “servant”). An *hyperetes* would be a servant who would be subordinate to the master. However, it matters not which word Paul uses. All three words portray a servant who must do the bidding of the master.

While a servant would be subordinate to his or her master, a servant could nevertheless be a significant person in his/her own right. For instance, the servants of a king would include military officers, counselors, administrators, and ambassadors. If a king were to send such a person to do something, the king would expect people to give that servant their full cooperation. In other words, the servant would carry in his/her person something of the authority of the king. The king would regard an insult to his servant as an insult to himself—and could be depended on to respond accordingly.²⁰ In this instance, Paul and Apollos are servants of Christ, “the King of kings, and Lord of lords” (1 Timothy 6:15; Revelation 17:14), so they carry in their persons something of the authority of Christ. These Corinthian Christians need to render Paul and Apollos the courtesies associated with the royal household with which they are associated. Otherwise, they can expect to be held accountable for insulting the servants of the King of kings.

The word *oikonomos* used by Paul in verse 1c “...and stewards (*oikonomos*) of God's mysteries” (*mysterion*) combines *oikos* (house) and *nemo* (distribute, apportion), and would be the administrator of a home or business. A steward (*oikonomos*), like a servant, is subordinate to a master, but there is a difference. A servant might be a person managing significant responsibilities, but some servants would do nothing more than wash dishes or sweep floors. However, a steward (*oikonomos*), by definition, has significant responsibilities. A steward is a person chosen by a master to exercise oversight over certain of the master's affairs. A steward might be charged with oversight of the palace and its staff—or the treasury—or the master's lands and livestock. The Old Testament tells us that Pharaoh appointed Joseph as steward over the financial affairs of Egypt. Joseph was responsible for managing the accumulated wealth of seven years of plenty so that Egypt might extend its

prosperity through the coming seven years of famine. So a servant might or might not have significant responsibilities, but a steward would always have significant responsibilities.

Paul and Apollos are “stewards of God’s mysteries” (*mysterion*). Paul uses this word, “mystery” (or “mysteries”) frequently (Romans 11:25; 16:25; 1 Corinthians 13:2; 14:2; 15:51; Ephesians 1:9; 3:3-5, 9; 5:32; 6:19; Colossians 1:26-27; 4:3; 2 Thessalonians 2:7; 1 Timothy 3:9, 16).

- In his letter to the Romans, Paul talks about “the preaching of Jesus Christ, according to the revelation of the mystery which has been kept secret through long ages, but now is revealed” (Romans 14:24-25).
- Later in this epistle, he will say, “Behold, I tell you a mystery. We will not all sleep, but we will all be changed, in a moment, in the twinkling of an eye, at the last trumpet” (1 Corinthians 15:51-52).
- In Ephesians, he says, “the mystery was made known to me, as I wrote before in few words, by which, when you read, you can perceive my understanding in the mystery of Christ; which in other generations was not made known to the children of men, as it has now been revealed to his holy apostles and prophets in the Spirit” (Ephesians 3:3-5).
- In Colossians, he talks about “the mystery which has been hidden for ages and generations. But now it has been revealed to his saints” (Colossians 1:26).

We might say then that, for Paul, a *mysterion* is spiritual knowledge that God has revealed—at least to some people. We might go another step to say that, for Paul, being entrusted with a *mysterion* revealed implies responsibility—stewardship.

God has entrusted certain mysteries to Paul and Apollos—has made them stewards of these mysteries. In his next letter to the Corinthians, he will say, “we have this treasure in clay vessels” (2 Corinthians 4:7)—the treasure being the Gospel and the clay jars being Paul and his co-workers.

Paul and Apollos can expect to be held accountable by God for their stewardship. Moreover, it is required of stewards that they be found trustworthy (“*pistos*) (v. 2). The concept of *pistis* means faith, fidelity, trust or faithfulness. While *pistis* means faith in God through Jesus Christ for Salvation of the human soul on the one hand, it also means the soundness of the mind in keeping faith or being faithful in all that one does. Another word that can be used complementarily with *pistis* or *pistoi* (faithfulness) is *dikaiois* and it means a state of being righteous or just.²¹ Righteousness has to do with doing what is right in the sight of God and man. It is even stated elsewhere in the Old Testament (Prov. 14:34) that: “Righteousness exalts a nation but sin or wrong doings is a reproach to a nation and even the people.” This is a wakeup call to all leaderships in sacred and secular spheres of the society to be awake to faithfulness in their administration of human and material resources.

Paul’s Message in 1 Corinthians 4:1-2: As a Psychological Model for Stewardship in the Nigerian Polity

The way Nigerians view politics and power needs to be transformed. Many Nigerians who venture into politics do so with the ideology of amassing wealth for themselves and using power for self-aggrandizement instead of serving the common good. Unfortunately, this is the syndrome that has plagued the minds and psyche of many Nigerians. In view of this, Paul’s message in 1 Corinthians is very relevant in ridding the minds of Nigerians of this plague. Paul as a leader of the Church corrected his followers about how himself and his co-workers should be regarded. Despite being leaders, Paul prefers to be seen as servants or stewards. This is an important lesson for Nigerians to learn. Leaders, in any capacity whether in government offices or civil service should consider themselves as servants and stewards who hold the people’s mandate.

Looking back at Nigeria’s socio-political trajectory, it is no fallacy that the leadership model that has been dominant for much of our history is that which is characterized with self-centeredness. Hence, despite the riches and natural endowments with which Nigeria has been providentially blessed, the benefits of our commonwealth have not been equitably distributed. Wide disparities of income persist and millions of Nigerians still live in grinding poverty.

Clearly, we need a new paradigm of leadership in Nigeria. We need a new definition of leadership which cuts to the core essence of the social contract between government and the governed, and recognizes that the

people have the power, and leaders are servants empowered by the people to do their bidding. As the old order that never worked for us is becoming obsolete, we need to embrace the emerging order of Servant Leadership and Stewardship characterised with accountability and transparency. We need to go back to the ideals of democracy; a government of the people, by the people and for the people.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The sort of paradigm of leadership that prevails in any society is predicated on how that society answers a vital moral question. Is power for self-aggrandizement or is it for serving the common good? If a society comes to believe that power is for self-aggrandizement, then public office and leadership will be marked by hyper-authoritarianism, corrupt enrichment and dysfunction. There is a clear difference between a leadership that preserves the common good and a leadership that promotes the affluence of a privileged minority. The former creates a climate of inclusion, unity and mutuality. The latter fosters imbalances, inequalities and inequity. In light of the forgoing, this paper suggests the following as way forward:

- i. There is need for Nigerian politicians and citizens to internalize Paul's message in 1 Corinthians 4:1-2 and change their behaviour in accordance with that teaching.
- ii. There is need for religious leaders to take front bonner for the said behavioural change of their subjects who doubles as both the masses and the political class. Nigerians are good followers and will key into whatever is modeled by our leaders, especially religious leaders. We do what we see our leaders do, not what we have been asked to do. If leaders lead with integrity, the message will be clear that this is a nation of honest people, who believe in hard work and in-tegrity. These values from the public sector will effectively translate into other spheres.
- iii. There is need for effective political education/ public enlightenment by the mass media. Political enlightenment of the citizens on continuous basis is essential to enable the masses understand their power to hold the leaders accountable and responsible. The masses should be made to comprehend that sovereignty belongs to them and that they have the legal authority to ask their leaders questions and get satisfactory responses on issues pertaining the management of public resources.
- iv. Effective use of whistle blowing should be encouraged. Whistle blowing is an effective and acceptable measure to promote transparency and accountability. The Federal Government should make sure that the identity of whistleblowers remains covert. The whistle blower protective act should be stringently adhered to so as to guarantee that whistleblowers are not in any way subjected to unjust treatment for blowing whistle.

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